

THE REALITY OF THE APPLICATION OF ELECTRONIC DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN GOVERNMENTAL INSTITUTIONS - AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE PALESTINIAN PENSION AGENCY

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Abstract— The research aims to identify the status of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - the study was applied on the Palestinian Pension Agency. The population of this study is composed of all employees in the Palestinian Pension Agency. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used the descriptive and analytical approach, through which try to describe the phenomenon of the subject of the study, analyze the data and the relationship between the components and the views put around it. Census method was used due to the small size of the study population and ease of access to the target group. (108) questionnaires were distributed to all members of the study population, were (65) employees in the Gaza Strip and (43) employees in the West Bank. All questionnaires were recovered.

The study found the following results: There were no statistically significant differences in the members of the population in response to differences in the study about the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case study on the Palestinian Pension Authority due to the age. There are no statistically significant differences in population members in response to the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case Study on the Palestinian Pension Authority due to the variable nature of the job. As well as there are no statistically significant differences in the members of the population in response to the study about the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case study on the Palestinian Pension Authority due to the variable of specialization. There are statistically significant differences in the study about the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case study on the Palestinian Pension Authority due to Qualification variable for the benefit of members of the population study who are

holding a Bachelor degree. There are statistically significant differences in the study about the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case study on the Palestinian Pension Authority due to the variable number of years of experience for the benefit of members of the study population who have experience between 11-15 years.

The study found a group of recommendations, including: the need to focus on the establishment of a general management of electronic documents in the organization structure that takes care of all the technical processes in it and contains scientifically qualified persons in the field of electronic document management. The need is for the attention in developing strategic plans, policies and mechanisms of action commensurate with the electronic document management system.

Keywords— Electronic document management system, the Palestinian Pension Authority, the State of Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the emergence of digital systems the so-called "computerizing documentation procedures" was found, which is based on transferring and registering, sorting and preparing of research computerized tools for documents saved electronically, thus they are retrieved quickly. Availability of data and information about them made dealing with them locally at first then remotely over networks later with collective documents at the same time which was the maximum an employee aspired in his office [24].

The Palestinian Pension Authority is an important institution in Palestine that is responsible for providing safety and social justice and ensuring a decent living for the individual and his family through social security. One of the most important systems on which the Authority depends on its work is the document management system. This system relies on dealing with documents and files, including the files of retirees - the beneficiaries whose services are terminated according to the various laws and legislations in Palestine - and the files of the employees - the files of the participants - the employees who are at the head of their business and pay the value of the monthly installment of the Authority under the various laws and regulations - (Insurance and Pensions Law and its amendments, 1968), the Law of Insurance and Pensions for the Palestinian Security Forces No. (16) of 2004, the Civil Retirement Law No. (34) for the year 1959, the Law on the Appropriations of the President of the Authority No. (18) For the year 2007, the law of salaries and bonuses of members of the Legislative Council No. (11) for the year 2005, and the law of general

retirement No. 072005), because the paper documents therein contain the information on which to calculate the benefits of retirees and benefits of participants and because of the multiplicity of laws and the advent of successive amendments (The public sector, the private sector, the security forces, the PLO, basic retirement, civil retirement, 2%, members of the Legislative Council and members of the government and the municipalities). It is always necessary to go to these documents to apply amendments for several reasons: The increase in the size of the paper archive, the increase in the process of cloning in several forms of paper copies at high costs and slow process, the storage of multiple stores (multiple and spaced archives) to store these paper files that require large and expensive spaces, the difficulty of follow-up and access to paper files, Geographical and political relations between the headquarters of the Authority in Palestine.

In the last decades of the twentieth century, with the advent of computers and the development of non-traditional new methods to save the necessary documents and archive them through the use of computer memory - digital memory - and the evolution of this new method with the development of mechanization of conservation and capacity of digital memory and the development of software for archiving and retrieval of information and documentation[19], and with the importance of the need for the agency personnel files, the development of a system for the management of electronic documents is the most important things that must happen as soon as possible as seen by the researchers.

2. RESEARCH PROBLEM

With the increasing inflation of the numbers and sizes of archives in the Authority; each file contains approximately 200 document in different sizes, and the slowness in dealing with the current archiving system, increased costs, and the possibility that its contents are lost after viewed by competent, and damage is certain to get on paper documents makes it more complicated to use, and the urgency of this historical paper files are concentrated in that it constitutes a system in terms of information administratively, so the integration of these files with the electronic records that are on the Authority database. The Information Technology in the Authority archived about one million, three hundred sheets out of five million paper and converted forms and manual applications electronically in public administrations to subscribers only by adding barcode to them and develop Authority programs to integrate with the electronic archiving system, and to date hand models in other departments have not been delivered to information technology department to convert them into

electronic documents and adding to them barcode and adding them to the archiving system which increases the problem of rising problem of manual papers and not entering them into the electronic archiving system.

3. RESEARCH QUESTION

Q1: What is the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - case study on the Palestinian Pension Authority?

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The hypotheses can be formulated as follows:

H1: There are significant differences between the averages of the responses of the respondents attributed to personal variables (age, the nature of the job, specialty, educational qualification, the number of years of service) in the Palestinian Pension Authority. It has the following sub-assumptions:

H1-1: There are statistically significant differences between the averages of respondents' responses due to the variable (age) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

H1-2: There are statistically significant differences between the averages of respondents' responses due to the variable (nature of job) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

H1-3: There are statistically significant differences between the averages of respondents' responses due to the variable (specialization) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

H1-4: There are statistically significant differences between the responses of the respondents due to the variable (qualification) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

H1-5: There are statistically significant differences between the responses of the respondents due to the variable (number of years of service) in the Palestinian Pension Authority

5. STUDY LIMITS AND SCOPE

Place Limitations: the study was conducted on the Palestinian Pension Authority.

Human Limitations: The study was conducted on the workers in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

Time Limitations: the study was conducted, preliminary data was collected, and statistical analysis was performed during the year (2017).

Subject (Academic) limitations: study the reality of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions Empirical Study on the Palestinian Pension Authority.

6. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Recognize the importance of electronic documents management system in governmental institutions in general and in the Palestinian Pension Authority in particular.
2. Show the advantages of the use of modern electronic documents management system and its benefits to ensure rapid delivery of services in the Palestinian Pension Authority.
3. Explore the differences between the averages of the respondents' responses attributable to personal variables (age, the nature of the job, specialty, educational qualification, the number of years of service).

7. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

1. This study derives its importance as this topic is of scientific and practical modernity and excellence alike.
2. Highlight the importance of the electronic document management system to keep the documents from damage and loss in the long term.
3. Recognize the reality of the application of electronic document management system in the Palestinian Authority Pension in Palestine.
4. Providing scientific and practical recommendations for the Palestinian Pension Authority in Palestine.

8. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The study of Ferwana [31] which aimed to investigate the impact of information and communication technology sector on the Palestinian Gross domestic product(GDP) during the period (2000-2014), through descriptive and analytical approach and the use of the standard curriculum in order to clarify relations between the independent variables (the number of fixed telephone, the number of mobile phone, Internet users, number of employees, intermediate consumption, production, compensation of employees, the number of operating institutions) and the dependent variable of economic growth, as measured by the Palestinian GDP. The study found a positive relationship between the variables: the number of mobile phones and intermediate consumption and the contribution of some moral and consistent variables with economic theory, but for the remainder of the variables were shown not to significantly these variables with other variables. The reason for this is due to the limitation in the model and modernity of technology sector information and

communication. Based on the results of the study the researcher recommends focusing on information and communication technology sector.

The study of Lubad [40] which was designed to identify the elements of the success of the e-government application in Palestine, the study sample was formed from 234 questionnaires obtained randomly from the study population, which is composed of senior management in ministries in the West Bank and Gaza Strip. The study found that one of the most important components of the success of the applications is the availability of vision, administrative and technical structure, human resources, adequate laws and regulations, e-government awareness and services, and the involvement of civil society organizations. The obstacles facing the applications: The unity of efforts between the West Bank and the Gaza Strip, the involvement of senior management in ministries and civil society institutions in the planning and implementation process, in addition to weakness in administrative and technical aspects, lack of adequate laws and legislation covering all fields of e-government, and the need for cadres. The study concluded with a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: the need to unify the strategy and geology of e-government applications between the West Bank and the Gaza Strip, enact laws and legislation sufficient to cover issues related to e-government; Human resources, and educating citizens about e-government and its services.

Study of Hamada [34] aimed at understanding the role of electronic transactions in the development of government performance in terms of increasing efficiency and effectiveness, enhancing transparency and increasing the quality of government services. The aim of this study is to know the availability of e-transactions requirements in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, and to identify the most significant problems faced by the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology in the process of transition to electronic transactions. The researcher used the descriptive analytical method and used the census method. The questionnaire was distributed to all 111 members of the study population. The study reached several results, the most important of which is that the requirements for the implementation of electronic transactions in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology related to administrative requirements, technical structure, financial resources and qualified human cadres trained in computerized applications and systems are available. The study also showed that most of the ministry's services are provided through electronic transactions, in addition to a positive relationship between the application of electronic transactions and the

development of performance through increasing efficiency and effectiveness, enhancing transparency and improving public service. The study issued a number of recommendations, including the need to enhance the skills and abilities of staff required to implement electronic transactions through a training plan.

A study of Ammar [26] aimed at finding out the applicability of the electronic management in the UNRWA agency in the Gaza Regional Office. A questionnaire was distributed to random sample of the study population of 225 questionnaires. The study revealed the existence of knowledge among the employees of the Agency in the electronic administration and the requirements of its success, in addition to the availability of the requirements and the financial, technical, human and administrative requirements for the implementation of electronic management. The study also showed the commitment and support of the senior management of the policy of applying electronic management and the study showed that individuals support the applications of electronic administration in terms of security, and showed that the use of electronic management. The efficiency of the job performance is greatly improved through the speed of completion of the work, the increase in productivity, the speed and accuracy of the delivery of instructions, and the provision of time and effort of the staff. However, the study showed a weakness in the incentive system in the Agency for those who excel in work, there is a lack of senior management in the participation of all administrative levels (different functions) in the development of objectives and programs related to the application of electronic management. The study has led to a number of recommendations, including: increasing the financial support necessary to train employees and qualify them to apply electronic management, develop an effective incentive system for those distinguished in electronic work, and the need to develop clear legislation and policies to protect privacy and protect infringements and security violations to increase confidence in Electronic transactions, and the need for participation of all administrative levels in the development of goals and programs related to the application and use of electronic management.

A study of Ghorabi [33] in which the researcher dealt with the reality of electronic archiving in Saudi Arabia in ministries and semi-governmental institutions in terms of: the equipment on which electronic archiving systems are based, the reality of their employees, the obstacles that limit the application of electronic archiving, and the importance of electronic archiving as a prerequisite for the development of e-business. The survey method was used to achieve the objectives of the study. It relied

on the questionnaire in all the data from a sample of (37) governmental and quasi-governmental bodies in addition to the use of the interview and observation tools. The study concluded with a number of conclusions and recommendations, the most important of which are: The National Center for Documentation and Archives in Saudi Arabia (Legislative and regulatory texts) and to strive to produce clear legislation on electronic document and archiving.

The study of [1] focused on the archiving concept in developed countries, which depends on the care of documents from the moment of its establishment in the departments and other governmental and public bodies, and the follow-up of these documents until their final fate is decided either by permanent conservation or destruction. It also presented pilot experiences in the use of digital systems in the documentation and archiving centers, national libraries and the advantages of digital systems. He pointed out that three things must be balanced: document preservation - cost - ease of use when the archive is oriented towards digital systems. Then display digital media used in document processing (magnetism, photovoltaic), equipment, software, Internet archives. He went on to recommend that the role of the Arab Archive should prepare itself to face future prospects, the criteria for confidentiality, and ways to make the document and the rights of its retrieval.

9. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

9.1 Records Management and Archives

The administrative documents source is one of the most important sources of information in the modern era. That it Contains information that is not contained in other sources, such as books, for example. These documents are produced in a formal way within official bodies in accordance with the laws of formal legislation; hence documentation information is characterized with accuracy and confidence. Information technology is a manifestation of public and private investment in all areas, both at the administrative, social and economic level etc., which in turn enables the society to make wide and important changes.

Monitoring and follow-up and comparing the rapid development and expansion of information technology that led us to the industrial revolution. This expansion has a significant impact on society, and advances in modern technology have the potential and radical impact on how people work and teach them how to live and learn in the light of modern technological developments [31]. Administrative documents record the facts as they occur. The latest information from statistics and reports on some of

the topics that may be the subject of research, before they are included in articles, books or even academic theses [17].

On the other hand, some of these documents will continue their journey through time by virtue of their survival as historical witnesses, and thus become an archival repository of national archival institutions as the most precious and most valuable state owned by the sources of its national history. Under the auspices of the state, and allocates to them spare areas, and is spent on protecting them and preparing the means to find them suitable. It is therefore necessary to reconcile the process of selection that will result in the selection of collections of documents that will become part of the archival collections of the archives and even part of the nation's heritage and the sources of its history and civilization [25].

9.2 Document Management

There must be a corporate objective that all employees work towards it. To achieve this goal, the management functions (planning, supervision, coordination, communication, organization) must be applied in the organization. The most important of these functions is the presence of a boss or supervisor of work or manager. Do not leave the freedom for everyone to work towards achieving his goal in the way he likes, otherwise the result would be a kind of conflict and chaos of different and different specialties and qualifications of workers [35].

The organization of all document activities (document production, classification, preservation and migration) is scientifically structured to make documents and their information a means of doing business, not a reason to block them. Document management without a scientific organization of documents will confuse work and make it difficult to access the document or information[25].

9.3 The purpose of document management

- Ease of self-identification and early documentation evaluation by providing the archive with detailed information about the organization's overall documentation.
- Ease of separation of important documents from those of no importance and prevent the archive from being flooded with the necessary documents.
- Work to make documentation accessible and to reduce the cost of administrative document service.
- Provide archivists with the necessary data, enabling them to plan well for the place, staff and other needs.

- Ease of basic archiving functions relating to order, description, reference and maintenance systems [32].

9.4 Organization of documents

A process of scientific control of documents resulting from the performance of works and activities from production to processing, maintenance and transfer to them to archiving or consumption which is a dynamic science that addresses the information in order to make use of them now and in the future efficiently and effectively at the lowest costs [25].

9.5 The concept of electronic documents

Electronic documents system like any manual system that save documents in terms of use of the public structure of the means of saving documents, which includes Cabinet, Drawer, and Folder, which files are saved in them, and Files, and finally Documents that is the work of scanning them using a Scanner.

The management information systems dealing with data and documents that exceed one of the original sources in the organization, whether produced by the organization in the context of their work or received through the external environment. Dealing with this data and documents is done through the information system of the organization to prepare plans, operating procedures, transaction, and adjusting the flow of data and documents into the organization by adjusting the documentary cycle and measures the performance of administrative activities, while facilitating the means of control of these procedures and follow up its implementation. So we find that the purpose of information systems not only carry out the monitoring, collection, processing and storage, but the ultimate goal lies in the recovery and circulation and broadcast selective operations of information and documents when you need to end user, where sophisticated systems designed to provide immediate and accurate answers in the light of the documents and data stored in the database. In addition to automating procedures to save time and effort secrecy and ensure when dealing, which determine the paths by which the completion of the procedures within each department and division in the organization through the so-called electronic document system, which manage data and documents within the organization since its inception or received until completed thus avoiding many of the problems of manual Archiving [50].

9.6 Electronic archiving objectives

The two main goals of Electronic archiving are [20]:

The strategic objective of electronic archiving is reaching paperless environment, electronic government without movement, queues, nor paper documents.

Immediate goal of the institution of electronic archiving is facing a massive flow of documents and control of the stacked archival by processing, saving, and retrieving it quickly.

The electronic archive supposed to speed the processing of documents by indexing them automatically, store them in more than one original copy, and distribute these "original" copies to the various parties concerned. Therefore the employee is no longer afraid of slow access to the document. The document retrieval became more rapid and in a diverse ways. The document which is not ranked considered in the science of archival lost piece of information and how can a person control the order of millions of documents and save them without using electronic archiving system?

9.7 Mechanisms of transformation to electronic archiving

The electronic archiving is divided into two main phases [18 and Almothem, 2012):

First: Planning stage for electronic archiving:

They can also be subdivided as follows:

- The study and survey phase: It is the inventory of the documents to be digitized, and the quantity, shapes and types that var according to color, size, paper quality, etc.
- The analysis phase: It is the comprehensive inventory of documents. It consists of setting priorities for the conversion of documents from paper to electronic and preparing lists containing basic data such as location, addresses of presence and preservation, degree of activity, etc.
- The plan building phase: The establishment of a plan for the preservation of documents, i.e., the time rules for the duration of their preservation, the date and the final determination of their fate, the date of their destruction or their deportation, etc., as well as the definition of a classification system for documents, when searching and retrieving the document.
- The phase of selecting the necessary software and gear: It includes computerized equipment and specialized software in the electronic disposal of documents and digital systems, the necessary databases, the development of appropriate fields, selection of search tools and the preparation of required reports ... etc.

- Databases Preparation phase: The preparation of databases that will include the preservation and processing of electronic documentation.

Second: the operational stage of e-archiving:

AL-Regeb explained the operational phase of e-archiving as follows [22]:

10. Preparation of paper documents from places of preservation or their presence to the place designated for the implementation of the project:

5. The collection of documents according to a specific classification (format, color, size, etc.) is carried out at this stage, with various documentary data and documents, and the exclusion of duplicated documents that cannot be duplicated.

6. Copy old documents that are difficult to scan directly or that do not include clarity in aspects of them to be addressed and clarified through tools and programs such as Photoshop.

7. Remove pins from the documents to be scanned.

8. Separate documents into groups by size, color, face, etc.

9. Marking documents to identify them and facilitate their return after the end of the project.

10. Encoding documents prepared for scanning according to a predetermined classification system.

11. Scanning phase: Scanning is carried out through a scanner and through a specialized system where techniques such as light, color, quality, etc. are used to convert the document from paper to digital image, to store the digital image on computers and to process it in the integrated digital system.

12. Quality control phase: A phase in parallel with photography where the quality of the digital documents is checked and compared to the original document to determine the defects in content or in the quality of the imaging, and if a shortage is noted then a re-imaging is done.

13. Indexing phase: A stage of data entry for digital documents through the completed database. It is a physical and descriptive indexing and document indexing. It is based on specific specifications for the purpose, or on the basis of specialized systems (software). It can be through the bar codes. With their data. Hypertext is also used to link documents to other files and distribute them for work and research or through relationships with database management systems.

14. The process of returning documents to their origin: This process is the return of files and documents that were in the process of scanning to some of them and to their origin before the scanning, by re-stapling after decomposition of some of them.

15. Storage: The storage phase of documents is carried out in different storage media, including the same computer memory, magnetic and compact disks as well as central systems, which is the backup method [29].

9.8 Advantages and disadvantages of electronic documents

Advantages and disadvantages of electronic documents Automated saving lacks legal credibility to the outputs, where so far it does not count the output of the computer before the courts unless they are certified with signatures and seals, as well as the possibility of modifying and changing in what is dealt with in automated systems in the event of failure to tighten supervision and control of the system, but automatic saving of documents and files features many advantages including [23]:

- Eliminating the problems of saving and dealing with manual files which results in damage, loss, theft, or other manual trading risks.
- Participation at the level of the file subject, the documents, and data related to the topics.
- Elimination of the problems of saving provides spaces of up to 90%.
- Define password for each user.
- Define password for each and every application archive of software applications within an organization.
- Define paths for the sessions of documents between more than one user.
- Characterize attachments tracks that are on the basis of documents to go through.
- Dealing, retrieving, transmitting capabilities and speed of transfer of documents and information to others in multiple locations in real time.
- Management of documentary cycle since its inception and until the completion of all the procedures and the possibility to follow all the procedures on the network, and print the report for all stages of the documentary cycle.
- Quick access to the substantive content of files and information directly due to the classification and indexing systems used.
- Access to reports and statistics and comparative tables easily and conveniently through the databases that contain data and all related organization documents.
- Elimination of chronological and geographical separation between the categories of beneficiaries to meet the immediate needs of the information and documents.

- Make connections with others at the same time without problems in the transmission of documents and information.
- The integration, coordination in handling operations of documents and information within and outside the organization.
- Provide an opportunity for employees to deal with the technical regulations of the documents and information at the international level through their dealings with other local and international organizations.
- Provide selective broadcasting of information and documentation services immediately after the data and documents updated.
- Confirm the credibility and validity of the technical systems for documents and information when dealing with others with high confidence.
- Accuracy, speed, insurance and maintaining files and information against all types of risk by the existence of alternative copies in multiple places.
- Save time, effort, and the rationalization of fiscal expenditure, including works to improve the economic optimum utilization of available resources.

16. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES

16.1 Research methodology:

The research aims to identify the status of the application of electronic document management system in governmental institutions - Study applied on Palestinian Pension Agency, and in order to achieve the goal of the study, the researchers used the descriptive and analytical approach in conducting the study since it commensurate with the phenomenon in question, as well as the researchers used primary and secondary sources to gather data for the study[2,3,5-10,27-30, which will process the raw data using appropriate statistical analysis methods to the objectives of the study[11-16,30,39,41-49], including the percentage distribution Recurring and arithmetic means, and through the use of SPSS statistical software and extracting the results.

16.2 Population and sample of the study:

The study population consists of all 128 employees of the Palestinian Pension Authority (Gaza Strip - West Bank) who hold administrative positions. The number of 20 employees in service positions (guard, reporter, driver, and companion) has been excluded because their responses are not of research value in relation to the research topic. Table 1 shows the distribution of the population and the sample of the research by regions.

Table 1: Distribution of population of the sample by region

No. Area Number of Employee:

11.	<u>Gaza</u>	<u>80</u>
12.		<u>West Bank (Ram Allah) 48</u>
Total		<u>128</u>

Source: Researchers from the preparation depending on the Authority statistics 2017 Table (1) shows that the researchers used the census method in the distribution of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to the administration in the Commission, represented by the following names: (Chairman of the Board, Minister, Director General, Department Director, Head of Department, Division, Assistant Head of Division, Chief Writer, Writer, Engineer, Programmer, Accountant, Lawyer, Executive Secretary, Secretary). The researchers distributed 108 questionnaires as follows: (65) employees at the Authority's headquarters in the Gaza Strip, (43) staff in the Ramallah and Hebron headquarters in the West Bank which represent the study population, and thus the researchers used a census method in distributing the questionnaire. (108) questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed with recovery rate 100%.

10.3 Characteristics of the research sample

First: The statistical description of the research sample according to characteristics and personal characteristics.

The following is a description of the characteristics of the research sample according to age, the nature of the job, the scientific qualification, the number of years of service, and specialization in the body under study.

Table (2): Statistical description of the research sample according to characteristics and personality characteristics (n = 108)

Characteristics and personality characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Order
M .	<u>Male</u>	<u>78</u>	<u>72.22</u> <u>1</u>
Gender	<u>Female</u>	<u>30</u>	<u>27.78</u> <u>2</u>
<u>Make a decision</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>0.9</u>	<u>4</u>
<u>Consulting</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>3.7</u>	<u>3</u>
Nature of the job	<u>Administrative</u>	<u>98</u>	<u>90.7</u> <u>1</u>
	<u>Other</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>4.6</u> <u>2</u>
<u>Secondary and lower</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>11.1</u>	<u>2</u>
A	<u>Average Diploma</u>	<u>6</u>	<u>5.5</u> <u>2</u>

Qualification	BA	82	75.9	1
	Postgraduate	8	7.4	3
5-1		18	17.5	2
Number of years of service	10-6	40	37.0	1
	15-11	14	12.9	4
	16 and more	35	32.4	3
Administrative and economic sciences		68	62.9	1
Specialization	Engineering /	14	12.9	4
	Legal sciences	6	5.5	3
Other		20	18.5	2

Table 2 shows that males accounted for 72.22% of the total study population. The researchers believe that there are tasks in the Authority that require high physical abilities due to the size and continuity of work. Therefore, the administration tends to identify the masculine element more than the female component. This result met with the study of Hamada [34], which shows the predominance of the male component of the highest percentage of employees in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, indicates that some departments need males for the nature of work, including technical support work over the 24 hours, Which leads to a preference for the male component of the female component of employment, which is consistent with Abu Ouaili [6], where the proportion of this component has reached 92.75%, while the proportion of females was 27.78% of the total sample and this ratio is high compared to the study Abu Ouaili [6]. The researchers believe that the nature of work for females represented by their direct handling of internal and external documents and correspondence differed with the study of Abu Ouaili [6] in that the Authority is an institution that is sometimes subject to like other ministries to the assignment of women from the General Staff office, and favoritism in the appointment.

The percentage of decision-making job was 0.9% of the total population of the study. This indicates that the decision maker is the president of the Commission only. This is consistent with the study of [1], while the percentage of advisory posts was 3.7% of the total sample. The administrative jobs are 90.7% of the total sample and this is consistent with the research objectives so that the core of the work in the Authority focuses on the administrative category.

The percentage of employees with a public secondary school and less reached 11.1% of the total study population. The researchers believe that this proportion is a little high and may be attributed to the reason for the small rise of this proportion that the owners of these qualifications are of old ages and this is consistent with the study of [1]. In this case, most of the employees are concerned with the conditions of family life, and the percentage of those with a diploma is 5.5% of the total sample. Most of them are between the ages of 35 and 45. The researchers believe that the owners of this group worked in the early stages of the establishment of the Commission have good practical experience. The percentage of those holding a bachelor's degree and above was 75.9% of the total sample, which is high. The researchers believe that the increase in the number of universities in Palestine gave more opportunities for students to obtain a bachelor's degree. Hamada [34] showed that the level of advanced education for employees in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology in addition to the conditions and specifications of the job in most of the jobs in the organizational structure of the ministry on the need to get the bachelor degree, which encouraged many employees with Diploma or less to obtain it in the Authority, and this is consistent with the study Ghorabi [33], which shows the extent of the administration's encouragement of scientific development. The Commission provided financial support to all graduate students in local or foreign universities.

The percentage of employees with less than 6 years of service is 17.5% of the total sample, while the percentage of those with years of experience from 6-10 years is 37.0% of the total sample. The researchers believe the most important work of the Commission relies on this group, and it is consistent with the study of Hamada [34] that the recent awareness of the category of 5-10 years of employees caused by the appointment of a large group of young people resulting from the political division between the West Bank and Gaza Strip and the interruption of most of the employees of the Gaza Strip to work. The percentage for those with experience ranged from 11-15 years is 12.9% of the total sample and the percentage of those with experience 16 years and over is 32.4% of the total sample. In view of these percentages, 82.3% of the sample members have sufficient years of experience in their fields of work. Therefore, the researchers believe that this will increase confidence in the results of this study. This is consistent with the study objectives were the proportion of those with sufficient experience to perform tasks with more than 5 years is estimated 91.1%.

The proportion of employees with a specialization in administrative and economic sciences is 62.9% of the total sample while the proportion of employees obtaining the specialization of engineering / information technology is 12.9% of the total sample. The proportion of employees with a specialization in legal sciences is 5.5% of the total sample. Employees with other specialties are 18.5% of the total sample. In view of these percentages, we find that the largest proportion of the sample items have a specialization in administrative and economic sciences, which indicates the extent of the Commission's keenness to select its cadres to be suitable for the nature of the work they are practicing. This is in line with the study of Abu Khalaf [4] and Ammar [26] were most of the supervisors and staff of the Agency are qualified and have the ability to adapt to the transformation of university operations and manual agency into electronic; therefore, after identifying the work they do, we find that they rely heavily on the current document management system and because of the increasing workload and number of termination files (civilian employees, Security Forces, PLO) they suffer in the Commission from the slow process handling termination files in each department of the Authority, especially in the Settlement and Disbursement Department, which is the bottleneck in the life of the file; in order to determine the type of benefit that the pensioner will receive (pension, bonus, pension only, bonus only). The researchers believe that the Commission urgently needs an electronic system for handling administrative documents that manages, organizes, facilitates, accelerates and reliably handles files.

17. ANALYSIS OF THE PARAGRAPHS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The following tables show the percentage of the alternatives for each paragraph as well as the mean, the relative weight and the sig value of each paragraph. Since the data are descriptive, the researchers used the sign test, which is a non-parametric test that corresponds to the nature of the ordinal data. The paragraph is positive in the sense that members of the study community agree to its content, if "the number of members of the study population is greater than the neutral value (3)", is greater than the "the number of members of the study population is less than the neutral value (3)" and the level of morality is less than or equal to (0.05). The paragraph is negative in the sense that members of the study population do not agree if "the number of members of the study population below the neutral value (3)" is greater than "the number of members of the study population is greater than the neutral value (3)" and the level of morality is less than or equal to (0.05). If the level of significance is

greater than (0.05) this indicates that the value is centered around the neutral value (3).

Test the hypotheses of the study

H1: There are statistically significant differences between the averages of respondents' responses attributed to the personal variables (age, nature of employment, specialization, academic qualification, number of years of service) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

It has the following sub-assumptions:

H1-1 test: There are statistically significant differences between the responses of the respondents due to the variable (age) in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

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